

NOVEL ANHYDRIDE-FUNCTIONALIZED POLYHEDRAL OLIGOMERIC SILSESQUIOXANE AS POTENTIAL NANO-FILLER IN PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

J K H Teo¹ and X Lu^{1,*}

¹ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Nanyang Technological University, 50 Nanyang Avenue, Singapore 639798

* To whom the correspondence should be addressed; tel: +65 6790 4585; fax: +65 6790 9081; e-mail: asxhlu@ntu.edu.sg

SUMMARY

The preparation of novel aromatic POSS-anhydride epoxy resins based on 5-(2,5-dioxotetrahydrofurfuryl)-3-methyl-3-cyclohexyl-1,2-dicarboxylic acid anhydride have been reported. Tests have shown that resin properties such as thermal stability, glassy modulus and coefficient of thermal expansion generally improved with POSS loading.

Keywords: polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane, epoxy, anhydride, imidization, nano-filler

INTRODUCTION

The past few decades have seen a steady upwards trend in the speed and performance of the integrated circuit (IC) devices, translating to complex designs that require very high I/O and performance packages. Previous packaging technologies are no longer enough. In recent years, there has been increased use of flip-chip technology as the most viable answer to the performance crunch [1].

Maintaining low costs is a key factor in enabling widespread adoption of the flip-chip technology. Popular manufacturing techniques such as direct chip attach (DCA) where the IC is directly attached to a low-cost organic substrate such as the FR-4 printed circuit board (PCB) is used. However, the large coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch between the silicon chip and the organic substrate severely diminishes the reliability of the flip-chip. Current flip-chip technologies make use of an epoxy-based underfill encapsulant, highly filled with silica, placed between the PCB and the silicon chip *via* capillary action to reduce the stresses arising from the differences in the CTE between the substrate and the chip [1, 2]. The underfill encapsulant also acts to protect the chip from moisture, ionic contaminants, radiation, thermal and mechanical stresses, shock and vibration.

However, reflow of solder bumps, and filling and cure of the underfill encapsulants are separate processes which result in decreased production efficiency. The tiny capillary force also limits the flow rate and distance of the underfill encapsulants due to high viscosity due to the large amount of fillers. This limits the chip size,

consequently becomes a bottleneck in flip-chip production. The no-flow underfill (NFU) process has been invented to circumvent the problems [3, 4]. The NFU process allows the encapsulant material to be dispensed first onto the substrate and the reflowing of the solder bumps and curing of the underfill are performed simultaneously, as illustrated in Fig. 1. This helps to eliminate the limitations on the viscosity of the underfill materials, package size and also improves the production efficiency.

Fig. 1. Schematics of solder-bumped flip-chip on low-cost substrates with (a) conventional underfill; (b) no-flow underfill processes [2].

However, there has been no widespread adoption of the NFU process due to its present drawbacks. The encapsulant material is dispensed on the substrate before alignment of the component. Fillers are generally not preferred in a no-flow formulation as there will be assembly yield losses i.e. filler particles trapped between solder bumps and pads causing no connection. As a result, their global properties such as coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and moduli are likely to be poorer than its conventional counterparts. Several methods have been developed to overcome the problem such as using layered underfills [5] and precursors to form inorganic fillers during reflow [6]. However, these may lead to more complicated formulations and processing of the underfill material.

Epoxy nanocomposites based on polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (POSS) may present another possible alternative as a new class of NFU encapsulants. The advantage of these hybrid organic-inorganic materials is that the silica and the epoxy groups are combined into single-phase molecules. The use of single-phase underfill may greatly minimize the aforementioned problems. In addition, the characteristics of POSS materials such as high glass transition temperatures (T_g s), low density, excellent oxidation resistance and high mechanical strength will be a boon in improving the overall properties of the underfill material.

There have been several attempts at preparing NFU encapsulants based on POSS. Laine's group have recently developed an epoxy-based NFU material based on octaaminophenyl octasilsesquioxane (OAPS) and was able to achieve CTEs of 20-25 ppm/ $^{\circ}$ C [7, 8]. However, compared with epoxy/anhydride formulations, epoxy/amine

formulations are less common for NFUs due to their shorter shelf-life. In addition, solvents have to be involved in the mixing stage for their formulations, which may bring about increased steps in the NFU process. Anhydride-cured epoxy formulations are more suitable as the cure reaction with epoxy is temperature controlled, thus minimizing premature cure below reflow temperatures, reducing device yield loss. They are also of higher thermal stability than amine-cured epoxies, with higher dielectric constant, lower shrinkage upon cure and stress-free systems. Jayaraman *et al.* have prepared underfills based on epoxy-functionalized POSS fillers that claimed good CTE reductions [9]. However, the POSS-epoxy monomers have very long and flexible groups which likely result in poorer CTEs. A plausible explanation for the improvements in CTE could be due to the inclusion of silica fillers which is not suitable for NFUs. With reactive groups on POSS, the dispersion and extent of cure of POSS monomers with the epoxy resin are dependent of cure kinetics [10, 11]. In a system where the kinetics difference between the POSS monomers and the epoxy matrix is large, inhomogeneity will increase, resulting in poorer properties. By functionalizing the POSS tethers with anhydride groups in an epoxy/anhydride system, the cure kinetics difference is smaller since the POSS behaves as an anhydride. As the anhydride groups do not homo-polymerize, the POSS monomers will be more evenly dispersed throughout the resin mixture. The properties of resultant nanocomposite will be improved. To the best of our knowledge, there has been no literature to date detailing the preparation of epoxy nanocomposites based on aromatic POSS-anhydride for packaging applications.

We herein report the preparation of aromatic anhydride-functionalized POSS epoxy nanocomposites (OEpPOSS) based on octaaminophenyl octasilsesquioxane (OAPS) and 5-(2,5-dioxotetrahydrofurfuryl)-3-methyl-3-cyclohexyl-1,2-dicarboxylic acid anhydride, with hexahydrophthalic anhydride (HHPA) as the curing agent. *N,N,N',N'*-tetraglycidyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenyl methane (TGDDM), a widely used epoxy in electronics packaging materials, was used as a co-monomer. The morphologies and resultant thermal and thermo-mechanical properties of the nanocomposites were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

OAPS was purchased from Mayaterials Inc. and further purified by reduction under ammonium formate and Pd/C. 5-(2,5-dioxotetrahydrofurfuryl)-3-methyl-3-cyclohexyl-1,2-dicarboxylic acid anhydride, thereafter known as EPICLON, was obtained from Merck Chemicals. TGDDM epoxy (EEW 110-115 g/ equiv.) and acetic anhydride were acquired from Sigma Aldrich. HHPA was purchased from Fluka.

The synthesis of the POSS-anhydride monomer, OEpPOSS, was carried out by imidization reaction between OAPS and EPICLON using a method slightly modified from Krishnan *et al.* [12]. In a 250 ml 2-necked round bottomed flask equipped with a magnetic stirring rod, the cycloaliphatic dianhydride, EPICLON (9.16 g, 34.6 mmol) was dissolved in 130 ml of anhydrous DMF at room ambient under dry N₂ environment. OAPS (2.0 g, 1.73 mmol), pre-dissolved in 20 ml of anhydrous DMF, was added dropwise into the reaction mixture. The reaction was stirred at room ambient for 6 h. The formed amic acid was chemically imidized. Then a catalytic amount of triethyl

amine was added (0.3 ml) and the reaction mixture was stirred well. Acetic anhydride (6.52 ml, 69.2 mmol) were then added dropwise. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stir for 2 days under constant N₂ bubbling at room temperature. Ethyl acetate (600 ml) was added and the resulting solution was washed four times with water. The organic layer was dried with magnesium sulphate and filtered. The solvent was removed *via* rotary evaporation and the solid was washed with 1:4 ethyl acetate/chloroform solution. The precipitate was filtered out and dried *in vacuo* at room ambient to yield a slightly yellow powder. FTIR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1776 (ν-C=O imide out-of-phase), 1710 (ν-C=O imide in-phase), 1377 (ν-C-N imide), 1233 (ν-C-O-C anhydride), 1119 (ν-Si-O-Si).

Scheme 1. Synthetic route of OEPOSS.

Preparation of POSS-anhydride nanocomposites

A stoichiometric ratio $r = 1.2$ of epoxy groups/anhydride groups was used for all samples in this study. The POSS-anhydride modified resins at 5, 10 and 15 mol.% were prepared by dissolving OEPOSS in HHPA at moderate temperature and the mixture was quenched in ice. *N,N,N',N'*-tetraglycidyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenyl methane (TGDDM) epoxy (EEW 110-115 g/ equiv.) was then added and mixed mechanically to yield a clear homogeneous mixture. The mixture was degassed *in vacuo* at ~ 40 °C and cured for 1 h at 140 °C in an air-circulating oven, thereafter post-cured for 24 h at 200 °C in an inert gas oven purged with argon. Their equivalent control samples were also prepared accordingly.

Characterization of nanocomposite resins

The samples were mixed with KBr powder and pressed into circular disks, and the FTIR spectra were obtained using a Perkin Elmer Instruments Spectrum GX Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometer at room temperature from 600 to 4000 cm⁻¹. A total of 50 scans were recorded at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ for averaging each spectrum.

The morphologies of the nanocomposites were studied under a JEOL JSM 6340F field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM). They were fractured cryogenically using liquid nitrogen and the fractured surfaces were coated with platinum before being applied to the SEM measurements.

Thermal and thermo-oxidative degradation of the cured resins were evaluated using a TA Instruments High Resolution TGA 2950 thermogravimetric analyzer over a temperature range of 100 °C to 800 °C in nitrogen and air environments respectively, at a heating rate of 20 °C/min. $T_d^{5\%}$ denotes the temperature at 5% weight loss. The char yield was taken at 700 °C.

Glass transition temperatures (T_g s) were determined using a TA Instruments DSC 2010 under nitrogen purge from 30 °C to 300 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The inflexion point of the transition region was taken to be the T_g s of the samples.

Viscoelastic measurements of the cured samples were recorded with a dynamic mechanical analyzer DMA Q800 from TA Instruments. The samples were polished to ~ 17.5 x 13.0 x 2.5 mm before being mounted on a single cantilever clamp and measured at a frequency of 1.0 Hz with a heating rate of 3 °C/min from room ambient to 300 °C.

CTE measurements were conducted using a TA Instruments TMA 2940 thermo-mechanical analyzer at a heating rate of 3 °C/min from room ambient to 250 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of OEpPOSS monomer

Fig. 2. IR spectra of (a) OEpPOSS; (b) OAPS.

OEpPOSS was prepared from the chemical imidization reaction between OAPS and the dianhydride EPICLON as described in Scheme 1. The dianhydride was added in excess (~2.5 times the stoichiometric ratio of OAPS) to lessen the likelihood of dimers (EPICLON-OAPS-EPICLON) and oligomers formation. As the components in the reaction mixture have similar solubilities, mixed solvents were employed to remove as

much excess starting material from the crude product as possible. As we were unable to isolate the product in its entirety, control samples containing EPICLON at various concentrations were used in this study to illustrate the effect of OEpPOSS on the properties on the POSS-modified resins.

The structure of OEpPOSS was not able to be fully elucidated by common characterization methods. Nonetheless, from the IR spectra shown in Fig. 2, the characteristic bands of OEpPOSS at 1119, 1233, 1377, 1710 and 1776 cm^{-1} , are assigned to Si-O-Si stretching vibration, C-O-C anhydride, imide C-N, and carbonyl (C=O in-phase and out-of-phase) respectively. The characteristic bands of OAPS at 3369 and 1119 cm^{-1} are assigned to N-H and Si-O-Si stretching vibrations respectively. The appearance of the characteristic bands of OEpPOSS and the disappearance of the OAPS bands indicated that the amic acid have been successfully cyclized to form OEpPOSS.

Morphology of POSS-anhydride resins

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of the fractured surfaces of POSS hybrids at: (A and D) 5; (B and E) 10; (C and F) 15 mol.% OEpPOSS concentrations.

The suitability of epoxy nanocomposites for NFU applications depends on whether a single-phase material can be achieved, thus the miscibility of the various components in the resin mixture is critical. The resin mixtures containing OEpPOSS were homogeneous and transparent at all POSS concentrations studied. When subjected to curing at elevated temperatures, it was observed that all samples were transparent, implying that the hybrid resins were homogenous i.e. no phase separation occurs at the scale more than the wavelength of visible light. The morphology of the POSS-anhydride modified resins were studied using FESEM with the SEM micrographs depicted in Fig.

3. It was observed that at 5 mol.% POSS concentration (A and D), virtually no localized POSS domains can be detected, suggesting that single phase material was likely obtained. With increasing POSS concentration (B and E, C and F), few irregular white regions around ~ 0.2 microns can be observed. They are likely POSS-rich clusters i.e. OEpPOSS oligomers formed during synthesis.

Thermal Stability

From Table 1, the degradation temperatures (T_{d5}) of the POSS-modified resins were observed to be lower than that of the control resins. A plausible explanation may be due to the non-uniform packing density of the POSS-modified network. Given that its modifiers are made up of OEpPOSS and excess EPICLON from the synthesis whereas that of the control samples consists of only EPICLON, the POSS-modified networks are more loosely packed, resulting in lowered cross-linking density per unit area than that of the control samples. Thus, when subjected to elevated temperatures, the initial degradation of the POSS-modified networks was faster than that of the control resins, resulting in lower T_{d5} .

Table 1. TGA data for the POSS hybrids in nitrogen and air.

Sample	$T_d^{5\%}$ (°C)		Char yield (%)	
	N ₂	Air	N ₂	Air
5 mol.% EPICLON*	355	352	5.1	0.0
5 mol.% OEpPOSS	351	332	7.9	2.1
10 mol.% EPICLON*	354	351	6.9	0.0
10 mol.% OEpPOSS	345	339	12.1	4.3
15 mol.% EPICLON*	351	344	11.3	0.0
15 mol.% OEpPOSS	339	336	11.0	2.7

From Fig. 4 depicting the TGA curve of 10 mol.% OEpPOSS resin, it can be seen that the oxidative environment promotes the formation of a protection layer earlier, as with the 5 and 15 mol.% OEpPOSS resins, shown by a shoulder band starting from ~ 400 °C. The hybrid resins show significantly reduced mass loss (~ 40 %) compared to the control resin ($\sim 22\%$), strongly suggesting that an inert protective barrier resulting from the degradation of POSS to silica has been formed, which prevents the fast spreading of heat in the hybrids and hence decrease the decomposition and gasification

rate. This has led to the POSS-modified networks exhibiting higher char yields at higher temperatures than their counterparts.

Fig. 4. Typical TGA thermograms of OEpPOSS resins under air atmosphere.

Thermal properties

Table 2. Summary of DSC, DMA and TMA values of the hybrid nanocomposites.

Sample	T_g (°C)	E' (GPa)				CTE (ppm/°C)	
		50 °C	100 °C	150 °C	200 °C	30-100 °C	100-150 °C
5 mol.% EPICLON*	216	2.7	2.5	2.2	1.9	60.2±1.6	69.5±3.7
5 mol.% OEpPOSS	214	2.8	2.4	2.0	1.7	59.0±2.4	68.2±3.4
10 mol.% EPICLON*	224	2.5	2.3	2.1	1.8	58.7±2.8	67.6±2.9
10 mol.% OEpPOSS	223	2.8	2.6	2.4	2.0	57.8±1.0	64.8±2.0
15 mol.% EPICLON*	215	2.9	2.6	2.3	1.9	59.6±1.4	66.3±3.5
15 mol.% OEpPOSS	216	3.2	2.9	2.6	2.1	55.4±1.7	63.5±1.8

* denotes control resin.

Table 2 summarizes the DSC, DMA and TMA data for the POSS-modified resins. No significant improvement in the glass transition temperatures (T_g s) can be observed at all POSS concentrations as compared to the control resins. A plausible explanation may likely due to competing factors i.e. the multi-functional POSS fillers provide increased cross-linking densities that hinder the segmental motion of the polymer chains but at the same time, the presence of the bulky POSS cages could also counteract as ‘plasticizers’ which aid in chain motion [13].

Dynamic mechanical analyses showed that the storage moduli (E') at the glass state of the POSS hybrids have generally improved as compared to the control resins. This may be attributed to the rigid POSS cages within the networks. The rigidity of the POSS hinders the relaxation of the polymer chains, resulting in higher moduli.

The TMA measurements indicate that with the addition of OEpPOSS into the epoxy networks, the CTEs were generally lowered. This was likely due to the inclusion of OEpPOSS in which the rigid aromatic POSS structures coupled with similarly rigid imide linkages contributed to the lowering of the expansion rate of the resins.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have prepared *via* chemical imidization a new class of POSS-anhydride modified resins based on octaaminophenyl octasilsesquioxane (OAPS) and 5-(2,5-dioxotetrahydrofurfuryl)-3-methyl-3-cyclohexyl-1,2-dicarboxylic acid anhydride, with hexahydrophthalic anhydride (HHPA) as the curing agent. The resultant hybrid resins showed improvements in thermal stabilities, storage moduli and lower CTEs than their counterparts. The enhanced properties demonstrated that the OEpPOSS-based epoxy resins may yet prove to be a new class of potential NFU encapsulants.

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